

Quality of final impressions for fabrication of removable prosthesis by general dental practitioner in Tripoli, Libya

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to examine the quality of final impressions, which had been made by private dental practitioner in purpose of fabricating of removable prosthesis in the Tripoli Libya. The study had been conducted within 5 dental laps that work with 25 private dental clinics. The inclusion criteria: the impression of the same day, impression for removable prosthesis and that used of acrylic custom tray. Exclusion criteria: the old impression, the impression that has been done by prosthodontic specialist and impression for fixed prosthesis. The evaluation of the impression has been done by three prosthodontic specialists, based on different factors that directly affect the quality of final impression. One hundred and fifty final impressions were evaluated, 42.7 % of the evaluated impression were evaluated as grade 1 (fair) (n=64) followed by grade 3 (very good) (n=35) 23.3% of the evaluated impression. And 21.3% of the impression (n=32) evaluated as grade 2 (good), 9.3 % of the impression (n=14) evaluated as grade 0 (poor) and only 3.3% of the evaluated impression (n=5) got the grade 4 score (excellent). Conclusion: The quality of final impression that had been sent to the dental laboratories for the fabrication of removable prosthesis was fair in Tripoli, Libya. There was a widespread use of inappropriate impression materials, technique and lack of experience of general dental practitioner.

Keywords: Impression , fabrication , removable prosthesis

INTRODUCTION

Patient studies demonstrate that millions of people lose their natural teeth, and may require prosthodontic treatment (Burton, 2000; Petropoulos and Rashedi, 2005). A review found that most patients are satisfied with the performance of conventional mucosal-borne complete dentures (Donovan et al., 2007). Most private practitioners have continued to use the denture fabrication methods which they learned in dental school, although often they modify their impression techniques to reflect the use of newer, more efficient and available materials.

An impression is a record, a facsimile of mouth tissues taken at an unstrained rest position or in various positions of displacement (Devan, 2005). The objectives of impression making are to capture all potential denture-bearing surfaces and tissues to provide support, retention, and stability for the denture under function. In the case of an edentulous arch, this requires a unique combination of managing movable soft tissue commensurate with integrating different materials and a technique for accurate reproduction. (Petrie et al., 2005).

The materials available for impression tray construction are as varied as are the materials for border molding and the final impression. More important than selection of material is the dentist's complete understanding of the concepts and principles in impression making (Zarb et al.,

1985; Lang, 1994; Boucher, 2004; Petropoulos and Rashedi, 2005; Al-Ahmad et al., 2006). The manner in which the impression was made may be more important than the material (Firtell and Koumjian, 1992; Ivanhoe et al., 2002).

Moreover, the production of an accurate final impression is regarded as an important milestone in the fabrication of complete dentures. The result of the final impression is multifactor as it depends on the skill of the clinician, as well as the appropriate selection and handling of suitable impression materials and trays (Basker et al., 2002). The skill of the clinician sign as proper setting of the tray, uniform pressure applied as well as proper border molding and how to communicate with the dental technician.

A survey in 1984, showed that only 30% of restorative dentists collectively (general dentists and prosthodontists) used a border-molded custom tray, 30% used a custom tray without border molding, and 30% used alginate in a stock tray for final impression (Taylor et al., 1984).

As a little contemporary information exists in relation to the quality of the fabrication of complete dentures in general dental practice and as the definitive impression consider one of the most important steps on the denture fabrication. The aim of this study was to evaluate the quality of final impressions, which had been made by private dental practitioner in purpose of

fabricating of removable prosthesis in the Tripoli Libya.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study had been conducted within 5 dental laps that work with 25 private dental clinics. The inclusion criteria were the impression of the same day, impression for removable prosthesis and that used of acrylic custom tray. We excluded the old impression, the impression that has been done by prosthodontic specialist and impression for fixed prosthesis.

The evaluation of the impression has been done by three prosthodontic specialists, base on different factors that directly affect the quality of

RESULTS

One hundred and fifty final impressions were evaluated, 53.3% of the impression (n=80) were made for the upper jaw and 46.7% of the impression (n=70) for the lower jaw. All the impression had been evaluated on a private basis. The evaluation of the impression had been done by three prosthodontic specialists.

As it shown in paragraph 1 the heights percentage were grade 1 (fair) (n=64) 42.7% of the evaluated

final impression, which include mixing of the material, surface texture, border molding, tray position, spread of material, pressure applied, present of tearing and including the anatomical land mark.

As no such study has been previously carried out in Libya, this investigation sought to provide baseline data in the area. . Hypothesis tests were carried out to investigate the quality of definitive impression that has been done by private practitioner.

impression followed by grade 3 (very good) (n=35) 23.3% of the evaluated impression. And 21.3% of the impression (n=32) evaluated as grade 2 (good), 9.3 % of the impression (n=14) evaluated as grade 0 (poor) and only 3.3% of the evaluated impression (n=5) got the grade 4 score (excellent).

Paragraph.1. showed the percentage of impression of different score. Score 0: poor, score 1: fair, score 2: good, score 3: very good and score 4: excellent

Regarding the material the results of statistical analyses are reported in table 1.

Rubber base impression material was mainly used to record final impressions 70.76% (n= 106)

of the examined impression, followed by zinc oxide eugenol 25.33% (n=38) and the less common use is alginate with 4% (n= 6) of the examined impression.

Table1 : Show the material used for final impression making.

	Z.O.E	Rubber base	alginate
Complete edentulous N=109	38	71	0
Partial edentulous N=41	0	35	6
Total N=150	38 (25.33%)	106 (70.67%)	6 (4%)

DISCUSSION

A fundamental pre-request for construction of removable prosthesis is the ability to record the accurate detail of the dental structure as well as denture foundation area, failure to record the oral detail may lead to construct low quality prosthesis.

The quality of master impression was found to be fair in the most evaluated impression (42.7%) (**Fig.1**) this rise up with a question about the quality of consequence denture.

However, the most common defect on the evaluated impression were the pressure applied as it was common to see pressure area on the impression (**Fig.2-3**) as well as lack of the border molding as about 80% of the evaluated impression didn't record the functional peripheries of denture foundation by border molding.

Moreover our result showed that only 3.3% of the evaluated final impression were have an excellent score (**Fig. 4**) as they were cover all the anatomical land mark with good record of functional periphery.

Although in 1977 survey reported that zinc oxide/eugenol paste was the most popular material for final impressions for complete dentures, followed by polysulfide, for both general dentists and prosthodontists in practice

(Harrison, 1977), our study showed that the polyvinylsiloxane impression material is the most common material was used in final impression for both partial and complete denture construction 70.7% of evaluated impression. That may coincide with the result of Solomon study in 1973 as he used silicone materials for complete denture impressions: a high viscosity material for border molding and a low viscosity material for final impression. He concluded that the silicone impression material was preferable over the conventional low-fusing impression compound (Solomon, 1973).

The introduction of guidelines form specialist sociality is essentially in aim to produce high quality removable prosthesis and improve the quality of life of edentate patient.

Fig . 1

Fig . 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

CONCLUSION

In this study, it was found that the quality of final impression that had been sent to the dental laboratories for the fabrication of removable prosthesis was fair in Tripoli, Libya.

There was a widespread use of inappropriate impression materials, technique and lack of

experience of the general dental practitioner. Further investigation into the educational needs of dental practitioners in Libya in respect of removable prosthesis construction is warranted.

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